

34.151% (33.93%)-Maximal Efficiencies, obtained in CdTe_{1-x}S_x, CdTe_{1-x}Se_x-Crystalline Alloy Junction Solar Cells at 300 K

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ABSTRACT:

In two new single $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x)-alloy junction solar cells at 300 K, [X(x)≡ CdTe_{1-x}S_x, CdTe_{1-x}Se_x], $0 \leq x \leq 1$, by basing on the same physical model-and-treatment method, as used in our recent works [1, 2], and also other works [3-11], some important results, obtained in the present work, are reported in the following.

As noted in Tables 2.1, 3.1, 4.1 and 5.1, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density $J_{oi(oII)}$ decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x, and decreases strongly with increasing x, for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. Further, as discussed in Eq. (45), at a same V_{oc} , both $J_{oi(oII)}$ and $n_{I(I)}$ have the same variations for same physical conditions.

In particular, at x=0, both $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdTe_{1-x}S_x(Se_x) alloys become the CdTe-crystal, as observed in Tables 1.1 and 1.2, and therefore, as given in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2, and 5.2, we get the same numerical results of $\eta_{I_{max.}(II_{max.})}$ [=26.182 % (25.92 %)], which can also be compared with the corresponding ones given in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ crystalline CdTe-junction solar cells [1, 2], as: $\eta_{I_{max.}(II_{max.})} = 23.14 \% (25.90 \%)$.

Further, at x=1 and for Sn⁺Cd (Cd⁺Sn), we obtain: (a) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdTe_{1-x}S_x alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I_{max.}(II_{max.})} = 34.151 \% (33.93 \%)$ and $T_H = 455.6 \text{ K} (454.1 \text{ K})$, as those given in Tables 2.2 (3.2), and (b) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdTe_{1-x}Se_x alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I_{max.}(II_{max.})} = 28.23 \% (28.22 \%)$ and $T_H = 418.0 \text{ K} (417.9 \text{ K})$, as those given in Tables 4.2 (5.2).

Finally, from above remarks, we can conclude that in order to obtain the highest efficiencies, the present (CdTe_{1-x}S_x, CdTe_{1-x}Se_x)-crystalline alloy junction solar cells could be chosen rather than the crystalline CdTe-junction solar cell [1, 2].

Keywords: (CdS_{1-x}Se_x, CdS_{1-x}Te_x)-crystalline alloy junction solar cells, single crystalline CdTe-junction solar cell, photovoltaic conversion factor, photovoltaic conversion efficiency.

Suggested Citation: H. Van Cong, "34.151% (33.93%)-Maximal Efficiencies, obtained in CdTe_{1-x}S_x, CdTe_{1-x}Se_x-Crystalline Alloy Junction Solar Cells at 300 K," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(2), pp. 125-149, Mar-Apr 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(2\).10](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(2).10)

INTRODUCTION

In two new single $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x)-alloy junction solar cells at 300 K, [X(x)≡ CdTe_{1-x}S_x, CdTe_{1-x}Se_x], $0 \leq x \leq 1$, by basing on the same physical model-and-treatment method, as used in our recent works [1, 2], and also other works [3-11], some important results, obtained in the present work, are reported in the following.

(i)-As noted in Tables 2.1, 3.1, 4.1 and 5.1, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density $J_{oi(oII)}$ decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x, and decreases strongly with increasing x,

for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. Then, as remarked in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2, at a same V_{oc} , the photovoltaic conversion factor, $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$, decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x , but it decreases strongly with increasing x , for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. In other words, as discussed in Eq. (45), at a same V_{oc} , both $J_{oI(oII)}$ and $n_{I(II)}$ have the same variations for same physical conditions.

(ii)-With such variations of $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$, as observed in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2, the maximal values of $\eta_{I(II)}$, $\eta_{I(II)max.}$ and the corresponding ones of the H-reservoir temperature, T_H , are obtained at $V_{oc} = V_{ocI(oCII)}$, being marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius.

(iii)-In particular, at $x=0$, both $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $CdTe_{1-x}S_x(Se_x)$ alloys become the CdTe-crystal, as observed in Tables 1.1 and 1.2, and therefore, as given in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2, and 5.2, we get the same numerical results of $\eta_{I(max.(IImax.)} [=26.182 \% (25.92 \%)]$, which can also be compared with the corresponding ones given in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ crystalline CdTe-junction solar cells [1, 2], as: $\eta_{I(max.(IImax.)} = 23.14 \% (25.90 \%)$.

(iv)-Further, at $x=1$ and for $Sn^+Cd (Cd^+Sn)$, we obtain: (a) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $CdTe_{1-x}S_x$ alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I(max.(IImax.)} = 34.151 \% (33.93 \%)$ and $T_H = 455.6 \text{ K} (454.1 \text{ K})$, as those given in Tables 2.2 (3.2), and (b) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $CdTe_{1-x}Se_x$ alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I(max.(IImax.)} = 28.23 \% (28.22 \%)$ and $T_H = 418.0 \text{ K} (417.9 \text{ K})$, as those given in Tables 4.2 (5.2).

(v)- Furthermore, from above remarks (iii) and (iv), we can conclude that in order to obtain the highest efficiencies, the present $(CdTe_{1-x}S_x, CdTe_{1-x}Se_x)$ - crystalline alloy junction solar cells could be chosen rather than the crystalline CdTe-junction solar cell [1, 2].

In the following, the energy band structure parameters and the dark minority-carrier saturation current density, due to the effects of x - concentration, impurity size, and heavy doping, the photovoltaic effect, and finally some numerical results and concluding remarks will be investigated.

ENERGY BAND STRUCTURE PARAMETERS AND DARK MINORITY-CARRIER SATURATION CURRENT DENSITY

First of all, in two single $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $X(x)$ - alloy junction solar cells, [$X(x) \equiv CdTe_{1-x}S_x, CdTe_{1-x}Se_x$], $0 \leq x \leq 1$, we present the effects of x -concentration on such $X(x)$ -alloy, donor (acceptor) [d(a)]-size, temperature T and heavy doping, affecting the energy-band-structure parameters [1, 2], in order to investigate the total minority-carrier saturation current densities, as follows.

A. Effects of x -concentration on such $X(x)$ - alloy

In the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ single $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $X(x)$ - alloy junction at $T=0 \text{ K}$, the intrinsic energy-band-structure parameters such as: the effective average number of equivalent conduction (valence)-band edges $g_{c(v)}(x)$, the unperturbed relative effective electron (hole) mass in conduction (valence) bands $m_{c(v)}(x)/m_0$, m_0 being the electron rest mass, the unperturbed relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_0(x)$, , expressed as functions of x , are given in the following.

(i)-The unperturbed relative effective electron (hole) mass in conduction (valence) bands are given by [1, 2]:

$$m_c(x)/m_0 = [m_{c(CdS)}/m_0]([m_{c(CdSe)}/m_0]) \times x + [m_{c(CdTe)}/m_0] \times (1 - x), \text{ and}$$

$$m_v(x)/m_0 = [m_{v(CdS)}/m_0]([m_{v(CdSe)}/m_0]) \times x + [m_{v(CdTe)}/m_0] \times (1 - x), \quad (1)$$

for the $[CdTe_{1-x}S_x]([CdTe_{1-x}Se_x])$ - alloy, respectively.

Here, one has: $m_{c(CdS)}/m_0=0.197$, $m_{c(CdSe)}/m_0=0.11$, $m_{c(CdTe)}/m_0=0.095$, $m_{v(CdS)}/m_0=0.801$, $m_{v(CdSe)}/m_0=0.45$, and $m_{v(CdTe)}/m_0=0.82$.

(ii)-The unperturbed relative dielectric constant of the intrinsic of the single crystalline X- alloy is found to be defined by [1, 2]:

$$\epsilon_o(x) = \epsilon_{CdS} (\epsilon_{CdSe}) \times x + \epsilon_{CdTe} \times (1 - x). \quad (2)$$

Here, one has: $\epsilon_{CdS} = 9$, $\epsilon_{CdSe} = 10.2$, and $\epsilon_{CdTe} = 10.31$.

(iii)-Finally, the unperturbed band gap is found to be given by [1, 2]:

$$E_{go}(x) \text{ in eV} = E_{gCdS}(x) [E_{gCdSe}(x)] \times x + E_{gCdTe}(x) \times (1 - x), \quad (3)$$

where $E_{gCdS}(x) = 2.58$ eV, $E_{gCdSe}(x) = 1.84$ eV, and $E_{gCdTe}(x) = 1.62$ eV.

Therefore, we can define the effective donor (acceptor)-ionization energy at $r_{d(a)} = r_{do(ao)}$ in absolute values as [1, 2]:

$$E_{do(ao)}(x) = \frac{13600 \times [m_{c(v)}(x)/m_o]}{[\epsilon_o(x)]^2} \text{ meV}, \quad (4)$$

and then, the isothermal bulk modulus, by:

$$B_{do(ao)}(x) \equiv \frac{E_{do(ao)}(x)}{(4\pi/3) \times (r_{do(ao)})^3}. \quad (5)$$

B. Effects of Impurity-size, with a given x

Here, due to the effects of $r_{d(a)}$ and x- concentration, all the energy-band-structure parameters will be expressed in terms of the effective relative static dielectric constant, $\epsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$, as follows.

At $r_{d(a)} = r_{do(ao)} = r_{Te(Cd)} = 0.132$ nm (0.148 nm), respectively, the needed boundary conditions are found to be: for the impurity-atom volume $V = (4\pi/3) \times (r_{d(a)})^3$, $V_{do(ao)} = (4\pi/3) \times (r_{do(ao)})^3$, for the pressure p, $p_o = 0$, and for the deformation potential energy (or the strain energy) σ , $\sigma_o = 0$. Further, the two important equations [1, 2, 6, 7], needed to determine the σ -variation $\Delta\sigma \equiv \sigma - \sigma_o = \sigma$, are defined by: $\frac{dp}{dV} = -\frac{B}{V}$ and $p = -\frac{d\sigma}{dV}$. giving: $\frac{d}{dV}(\frac{d\sigma}{dV}) = \frac{B}{V}$. Then, by an integration, one gets:

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{d(a)} &= B_{do(ao)}(x) \times (V - V_{do(ao)}) \times \ln\left(\frac{V}{V_{do(ao)}}\right) = \\ &= E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Furthermore, by using the effective Bohr model, we also shown [1, 2, 3, 4, 5] that, as $r_{d(a)} > r_{do(ao)}$ ($r_{d(a)} < r_{do(ao)}$), the compression (dilatation), being represented by: $\pm [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)}$, increases (decreases) the energy gap $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, and the effective donor (acceptor)-ionization energy $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ in absolute values, as:

for $r_{d(a)} \geq r_{do(ao)}$,

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)})} \right)^2 - 1 \right] = + [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)},$$

and for $r_{d(a)} \leq r_{do(ao)}$,

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)})} \right)^2 - 1 \right] = - [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)}. \quad (7)$$

Therefore, from Equations 6 and 7, one obtains the expressions for relative dielectric constant $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and energy band gap $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, as:

(i)-for $r_{d(a)} \geq r_{do(ao)}$, since $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\sqrt{1 + \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3}} \leq \varepsilon_o(x)$,

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 \geq 0, \quad (8a)$$

according to the increase in both $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, for a given x , and

(ii)-for $r_{d(a)} \leq r_{do(ao)}$, since $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\sqrt{1 - \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3}} \geq \varepsilon_o(x)$, with a condition, given by:

$$\left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 < 1,$$

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = -E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 \leq 0, \quad (8.b)$$

corresponding to the decrease in both $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, for a given x .

C. Effect of T, with given x and $r_{d(a)}$

Here, as given in our previous works [1, 2], the intrinsic band gap $E_{gin(gip)}(r_{d(a)}, x, T)$ is given by:

$$E_{gin(gip)}(r_{d(a)}, x, T) \text{ in eV} = E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - \frac{10^{-4} \times T^2}{T + 94 \text{ K}} \times \{7.0043 \times x + 4.3779 \times (1 - x)\}, \quad (9)$$

which decreases, for given x and $r_{d(a)}$, with an increasing T .

Furthermore, in the $n(p)$ -type $X(x)$ -alloy, one can define the intrinsic carrier concentration $n_{in(ip)}$ by:

$$n_{in(p)}^2(T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv N_c(T, x) \times N_v(T, x) \times \exp\left(\frac{-E_{gin(p)}(T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T}\right), \quad (10)$$

where $N_{c(v)}(T, x)$ is the conduction (valence)-band density of states, being defined as:

$$N_{c(v)}(T, x) = 2 \times \left(\frac{m_{c(v)}(x) \times k_B T}{2\pi\hbar^2}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \text{ (cm}^{-3}\text{)}. \quad (11)$$

So, the numerical results of $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, $B_{do(ao)}(x)$, $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $E_{gin(gip)}(r_{d(a)}, x, T)$, calculated using Equations (4), (5), (8a), (8b) and (9), are reported in following Tables 1.1 and 1.2 in Appendix 1.

Tables 1.1 and 1.2 in Appendix 1

D. Heavy Doping Effect, with given T , x and $r_{d(a)}$

Here, as given in our previous works [3-5], the Fermi energy $E_{Fn}(-E_{Fp})$, band gap narrowing (BGN), and apparent band gap narrowing (ABGN), are reported in the following.

First, the Fermi energy $E_{Fn}(-E_{Fp})$, obtained for any T and any $d(a)$ -density, $N_{d(a)}$, being investigated in our previous paper [3-5], with a precision of the order of 2.11×10^{-4} , is found to be given by:

$$\frac{E_{Fn}(u)}{k_B T} \left(\frac{-E_{Fp}(u)}{k_B T}\right) = \frac{G(u) + Au^B F(u)}{1 + Au^B}, \quad A = 0.0005372 \text{ and } B = 4.82842262, \quad (12)$$

where u is the reduced electron density, $u(N_{d(a)}, T, x) \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{c(v)}(T, x)}$, $F(u) = au^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(1 + bu^{-\frac{4}{3}} + cu^{-\frac{8}{3}}\right)^{-\frac{2}{3}}$, $a = \left[(3\sqrt{\pi}/4) \times u\right]^{2/3}$, $b = \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{\pi}{a}\right)^2$, $c = \frac{62.3739855}{1920} \left(\frac{\pi}{a}\right)^4$, and $G(u) \simeq \ln(u) + 2^{-\frac{3}{2}} \times u \times e^{-du}$; $d = 2^{3/2} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{27}} - \frac{3}{16}\right] > 0$.

Here, one notes that: (i) as $u \gg 1$, according to the HD [$d(a)$ - $X(x)$ - alloy] ER-case, or to the degenerate one, Eq. (12) is reduced to the function $F(u)$, and (ii) $\frac{E_{Fn}(u \ll 1)}{k_B T} \left(\frac{-E_{Fp}(u \ll 1)}{k_B T}\right) \ll -1$, to the LD [$a(d)$ - $X(x)$ - alloy] BR-case, or to the non-degenerate one, Eq. (12) is reduced to the function $G(u)$.

Secondly, if denoting the effective Wigner-Seitz radius $r_{sn(sp)}$, characteristic of the interactions, by:

$$r_{sn(sp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x) = 1.1723 \times 10^8 \times \left(\frac{g_{c(v)}}{N_{d(a)}}\right)^{1/3} \times \frac{m_{c(v)}(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)}, \quad g_{c(v)} = 1(1), \quad (13)$$

the correlation energy of an effective electron gas, $E_{cn(cp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x)$, is given as [6-7]:

$$E_{cn(cp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{-0.87553}{0.0908+r_{sn(sp)}} + \frac{\frac{0.87553}{0.0908+r_{sn(sp)}} + \left(\frac{2[1-\ln(2)]}{\pi^2}\right) \times \ln(r_{sn(sp)}) - 0.093288}{1+0.03847728 \times r_{sn(sp)}^{1.67378876}}.$$

Now, taking into account various spin-polarized chemical potential-energy contributions such as [6,7]: exchange energy of an effective electron (hole) gas, majority-carrier correlation energy of an effective electron (hole) gas, minority hole (electron) correlation energy, majority electron (hole)-ionized d(a) interaction screened Coulomb potential energy, and finally minority hole (electron)-ionized d(a) interaction screened Coulomb potential energy, the band gap narrowing (BGN) are given as follows.

Then, in the n-type HD X(x)- alloy, the BGN is found to be given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_{gn}(N_d, r_d, x) &\simeq a_1 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d,x})} \times N_r^{1/3} + a_2 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d,x})} \times N_r^{1/3} \times (2.503 \times [-E_{cn}(r_{sn}) \times r_{sn}]) + \\ &a_3 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d,x})}\right]^{5/4} \times \sqrt{\frac{m_v}{m_c}} \times N_r^{1/4} + a_4 \times \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d,x})}} \times N_r^{1/2} \times 2 + a_5 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d,x})}\right]^{3/2} \times N_r^{1/6}, \\ N_r &\equiv \left(\frac{N_d}{9.999 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (14n)$$

where $a_1 = 3.8 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_2 = 6.5 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, $a_3 = 2.8 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_4 = 5.597 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$ and $a_5 = 8.1 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, and in the p-type HD X(x)- alloy, as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_{gp}(N_a, r_a, x) &\simeq a_1 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{a,x})} \times N_r^{1/3} + a_2 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{a,x})} \times N_r^{1/3} \times (2.503 \times [-E_{cp}(r_{sp}) \times r_{sp}]) + \\ &a_3 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{a,x})}\right]^{5/4} \times \sqrt{\frac{m_c}{m_v}} \times N_r^{1/4} + 2a_4 \times \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{a,x})}} \times N_r^{1/2} + a_5 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{a,x})}\right]^{3/2} \times N_r^{1/6}, \\ N_r &\equiv \left(\frac{N_a}{9.999 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (14p)$$

where $a_1 = 3.15 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_2 = 5.41 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, $a_3 = 2.32 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_4 = 4.195 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$ and $a_5 = 9.80 \times 10^{-5}(\text{eV})$.

Therefore, in the HD[d(a)- X(x)- alloy] ER, we can define the effective extrinsic carrier concentration, $n_{en(ep)}^*$, by :

$$n_{en(ep)}^*(N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \sqrt{N_{d(a)} \times p_o(n_o)} = n_{in(ip)}(T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times \exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(aggp)}}{2k_B T}\right], \quad (15)$$

where the apparent band gap narrowing (ABGN), $\Delta E_{agn(aggp)}$, is defined by:

$$\Delta E_{agn}(N_d, T, r_d, x) \equiv \Delta E_{gn}(N_d, r_d, x) + k_B T \times \ln\left(\frac{N_d}{N_c(T,x)}\right) - E_{Fn}(N_d, T, x), \quad (16n)$$

$$\Delta E_{aggp}(N_a, T, r_a, x) \equiv \Delta E_{gp}(N_a, r_a, x) + k_B T \times \ln\left(\frac{N_a}{N_v(T,x)}\right) + E_{Fp}(N_a, T, x). \quad (16p)$$

E. Total minority-carrier saturation current density

In the two $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $X(x)$ - alloy -junction solar cells, denoted respectively by I(II), the total carrier-minority saturation current density is defined by:

$$J_{oI(oII)} \equiv J_{Eno(Epo)} + J_{Bpo(Bno)} \quad (17)$$

where $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ is the minority-electron (hole) saturation current density injected into the LD[a(d)- $X(x)$ - alloy] BR, and $J_{Eno(Epo)}$ is the minority-hole (electron) saturation-current density injected into the HD[d(a)- $X(x)$ - alloy] ER.

$J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ in the LD[a(d)- $X(x)$ - alloy]BR

Here, $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ is determined by [1, 2]:

$$J_{Bpo(Bno)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x) = \frac{e \times n_{ip(in)}^2(T, r_{a(d)}, x) \times \sqrt{\frac{D_{e(h)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x)}{\tau_{eB(hB)}(N_{a(d)})}}}{N_{a(d)}}, \quad (18)$$

where $n_{ip(in)}^2(T, r_{a(d)}, x)$ is determined Eq. (10), $D_{e(h)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x)$ is the minority electron (minority hole) diffusion coefficient:

$$D_e(N_a, T, r_a, x) = \frac{k_B T}{e} \times \left[850 + \frac{5750}{1 + \left(\frac{N_a}{8 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right)^{1.8}} \right] \times \left(\frac{\varepsilon(r_a, x)}{\varepsilon_o(x)}\right)^2 \text{ (cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}\text{)}, \quad (19a)$$

$$D_h(N_d, T, r_d, x) = \frac{k_B T}{e} \times \left[85 + \frac{1165}{1 + \left(\frac{N_d}{4 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right)^{0.44}} \right] \times \left(\frac{\varepsilon(r_d, x)}{\varepsilon_o(x)}\right)^2 \text{ (cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}\text{)}, \quad (19b)$$

and $\tau_{eB(hB)}(N_{a(d)})$ is the minority electron (minority hole) lifetime in the BR:

$$\tau_{eB}(N_a)^{-1} = \frac{1}{10^{-7}} + 3 \times 10^{-13} \times N_a + 1.83 \times 10^{-31} \times N_a^2, \quad (20a)$$

$$\tau_{hB}(N_d)^{-1} = \frac{1}{10^{-7}} + 11.76 \times 10^{-13} \times N_d + 2.78 \times 10^{-31} \times N_d^2. \quad (20b)$$

$J_{Eno(Epo)}$ in the HD[d(a)- $X(x)$ - alloy]ER

In the non-uniformly and heavily doped emitter region of d(a)- $X(x)$ devices, the effective Gaussian d(a)-density profile or the d(a) (majority-e(h)) density, is defined in such the HD[d(a)- $X(x)$ alloy] ER-width W , as [1, 2]:

$$\rho_{d(a)}(y, N_{d(a)}, W) = N_{d(a)} \times \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{y}{W}\right)^2 \times \ln\left[\frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{do(ao)}(W)}\right]\right\} \equiv N_{d(a)} \times \left[\frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{do(ao)}(W)}\right]^{-\left(\frac{y}{W}\right)^2}, \quad 0 \leq y \leq W$$

$$N_{do(ao)}(W) \equiv 7.9 \times 10^{17} (2 \times 10^5) \times \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{W}{184.2 (1) \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}}\right)^{1.066 (0.5)}\right\} \text{ (cm}^{-3}\text{)}, \quad (21)$$

where $\rho_{d(a)}(y=0) = N_{d(a)}$ is the surface d(a)-density, and at the emitter-base junction, $\rho_{d(a)}(y=W) = N_{do(ao)}(W)$, which decreases with increasing W. Further, the “effective doping density” is defined by:

$$N_{d(a)}^*(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \rho_{d(a)}(y) / \exp \left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(\rho_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T} \right],$$

$$N_{d(a)}^*(y=0, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{\exp \left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T} \right]}, \text{ and}$$

$$N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \frac{N_{do(ao)}(W)}{\exp \left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T} \right]}, \quad (22)$$

where the apparent band gap narrowing $\Delta E_{agn(agg)}$ is determined in Eq. (16), replacing $N_{d(a)}$ by $\rho_{d(a)}(y, N_{d(a)}, W)$.

Now, we can define the minority hole (minority electron) transport parameter $F_{h(e)}$ as:

$$F_{h(e)}(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2(T, r_{d(a)})}{p_o(n_o) \times D_{h(e)}} = \frac{N_{d(a)}^*}{D_{h(e)}} \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{D_{h(e)}} \times \left(\frac{n_{in(ip)}}{n_{in(ip)}^*} \right)^2 \equiv$$

$$\equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{D_{h(e)} \times \exp \left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}}{k_B T} \right]} \quad (cm^{-5} \times s), \quad (23)$$

the minority hole (electron) diffusion length, $L_{h(e)}(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)$ by:

$$L_{h(e)}^{-2}(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) = [\tau_{hE(eE)} \times D_{h(e)}]^{-1} = (C \times F_{h(e)})^2 = \left(C \times \frac{N_{d(a)}^*}{D_{h(e)}} \right)^2 = \left(C \times \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2(T, r_{d(a)})}{p_o(n_o) \times D_{h(e)}} \right)^2,$$

where the constant C was chosen to be equal to: $2.0893 \times 10^{-30} (cm^4/s)$, and the minority hole (minority electron) lifetime $\tau_{hE(eE)}$ as:

$$\tau_{hE(eE)} \equiv \frac{1}{D_{h(e)} \times L_{h(e)}^{-2}} = \frac{1}{D_{h(e)} \times (C \times F_{h(e)})^2}. \quad (24)$$

Then, under low-level injection, in the absence of external generation, and for the steady-state case, we can define the minority-h(e) density by:

$$p_o(y)[n_o(y)] \equiv \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}, \quad (25)$$

and a normalized excess minority-h(e) density $u(x)$ or a relative deviation between $p(y)[n(y)]$ and $p_o(y)[n_o(y)]$.

$$u(y) \equiv \frac{p(y)[n(y)] - p_o(y)[n_o(y)]}{p_o(y)[n_o(y)]}, \quad (26)$$

which must verify the two following boundary conditions as:

$$u(y=0) \equiv \frac{-J_{h(e)}(y=0)[J_e(y=0)]}{eS \times p_o(y=0)[n_o(y=0)]},$$

$$u(y=W) = \exp\left(\frac{V}{n_{I(II)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1.$$

Here, $n_{I(II)}(V)$ is a photovoltaic conversion factor determined latter, $S \left(\frac{cm}{s}\right)$ is the surface recombination velocity at the emitter contact, V is the applied voltage, $V_T \equiv (k_B T/e)$ is the thermal voltage, and the minority-hole (electron) current density $J_{h(e)}(y, r_{d(a)}, x)$.

Further, from the Fick's law for minority hole (electron)-diffusion equations, one has [1, 2]:

$$J_{h(e)}(y, r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{-e(+e) \times n_{in(ip)}^2}{F_{h(e)}(y)} \times \frac{du(y)}{dy} = \frac{-e(+e) n_{in(ip)}^2 D_{h(e)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x)}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, r_{d(a)}, x)} \times \frac{du(y)}{dy}, \quad (27)$$

where $N_{d(a)}^*(y, r_{d(a)}, x)$ is given in Eq. (22), $D_{h(e)}$ and $F_{h(e)}$ are determined respectively in Equations (19) and (23), and from the minority-hole (electron) continuity equation as:

$$\frac{dJ_{h(e)}(y, r_{d(a)}, x)}{dy} = -e(+e) \times n_{in(p)}^2 \times \frac{u(y)}{F_{h(e)}(y) \times L_{h(e)}^2(y)} =$$

$$= -e(+e) \times n_{in(p)}^2 \times \frac{u(y)}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, r_{d(a)}, x) \times \tau_{hE}(eE)}, \quad (28)$$

Therefore, the following second-order differential equation is obtained:

$$\frac{d^2 u(y)}{dy^2} - \frac{dF_{h(e)}(y)}{dy} \times \frac{du(y)}{dy} - \frac{u(y)}{L_{h(e)}^2(y)} = 0, \quad (29)$$

Then, taking into account the two above boundary conditions given in Eq. (22), one thus gets the general solution of this Eq. (29), as:

$$u(y) = \frac{\sinh(P(y)) + I(W, S) \times \cosh(P(y))}{\sinh(P(W)) + I(W, S) \times \cosh(P(W))} \times \left(\exp\left(\frac{V}{n_{I(II)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1 \right), \quad (30)$$

where the factor $I(W, S)$ is determined by: $D_{h(e)}(N_d, T, r_{d(a)}, x)$

$$I(T, r_{d(a)}, x, W, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(y=W, N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{S \times L_{h(e)}(y=W, N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}. \quad (31)$$

Further, since $\frac{dP(y)}{dy} \equiv C \times F_{h(e)}(y) = \frac{1}{L_{h(e)}(y)}$, $C = 2.0893 \times 10^{-30}$ (cm^4/s), for the X(x)-alloy, being an empirical parameter, chosen for each crystalline semiconductor, P(y) is thus found to be defined by:

$$P(y) \equiv \int_0^y \frac{dy}{L_{h(e)}(y)}, \quad 0 \leq y \leq W, \quad P(y = W) \equiv \left(\frac{1}{W} \times \int_0^W \frac{dy}{L_{h(e)}(y)}\right) \times W \equiv \frac{W}{L_{h(e)}^*(y)} = \frac{L_{h(e)}(y)}{L_{h(e)}^*(y)} \times \frac{W}{L_{h(e)}(y)}, \quad (32)$$

where $L_{h(e)}^*(y)$ is the effective minority hole (minority electron) diffusion length. Further, the minority-hole (electron) current density injected into the HD[d(a)- X(x) alloy] ER is found to be given by:

$$J_{h(e)}(y, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S, V) = -J_{Eno}(y, W, N_d, T, r_d, x, S) [J_{Epo}(y, W, N_a, T, r_a, x, S)] \times \left(\exp\left(\frac{v}{n_{I(I)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1 \right), \quad (33)$$

where $J_{Eno(Epo)}$ is the saturation minority hole (minority electron) current density,

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{\cosh(P(x)) + I(W, S) \times \sinh(P(x))}{\sinh(P(W)) + I(W, S) \times \cosh(P(W))}. \quad (34)$$

In the following, we will denote P(W) and I(W, S) by P and I, for a simplicity. So, Eq. (30) gives:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = 0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{1}{\sinh(P) + I \times \cosh(P)}, \quad (35)$$

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}{\sinh(P) + I \times \cosh(P)}, \quad (36)$$

and then,

$$\frac{J_{h(e)}(y=0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S, V)}{J_{h(e)}(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S, V)} \equiv \frac{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)} = \frac{1}{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}. \quad (37)$$

Now, if defining the effective excess minority-hole (electron) charge storage in the emitter region by:

$Q_{h(e)}^*(y = W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \int_0^W +e(-e) \times u(y) \times p_o(y) [n_o(y)] \times \frac{\tau_{hE(eE)}(N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}(\rho_{d(a)}(x), T, r_{d(a)}, x)} dy$, and the effective minority hole (minority electron) transit time [htt(ett)] by: $\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y =$

$W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x, S \equiv Q_{h(e)}^*(y = W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) / J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)$, and from Equations (24, 31), one obtains:

$$\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \equiv 1 - \frac{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)} = 1 - \frac{1}{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}. \quad (38)$$

Now, some important results can be obtained and discussed below.

As $P \ll 1$ (or $W \ll L_{h(e)}$) and $S \rightarrow \infty$, $I \equiv I(W, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{S \times L_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)} \rightarrow 0$, from Eq. (38), one has: $\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \rightarrow 0$, suggesting a completely transparent emitter region (CTER)-case, where, from Eq. (36), one obtains:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{1}{P(W)}. \quad (39)$$

Further, as $P \gg 1$ (or $W \gg L_{h(e)}$) and $S \rightarrow 0$, $I \equiv I(y = W, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{S \times L_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)} \rightarrow \infty$, and from Eq. (38) one has: $\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \rightarrow 1$, suggesting a completely opaque emitter region (COER)-case, where, from Eq. (36), one gets:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \tanh(P). \quad (40)$$

In summary, in the two $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x)-alloy junction solar cells, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density $J_{oI(oII)}$, defined in Eq. (17), is now rewritten as:

$$J_{oI(oII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, x) \equiv J_{Eno(Epo)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) + J_{Bpo(Bno)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x), \quad (41)$$

where $J_{Eno(Epo)}$ and $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ are determined respectively in Equations (36, 18). Further, the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*}{\tau_{hE(eE)}}$, $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$, $J_{Eno(Epo)}$, and $J_{oI(oII)}$, calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), as those given in Tables (2.1), (3.1), (4.1), and (5.1) in Appendix 1, respectively.

Tables (2.1), (3.1), (4.1), and (5.1) in Appendix 1

PHOTOVOLTAIC CONVERSION EFFECT AT 300 K

Here, in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x) -alloy junction solar cells at $T=300$ K, denoted respectively by I(II), and for physical conditions, respectively, as:

$$W = 0.1 \mu\text{m}, N_{d \equiv S(a \equiv \text{Cd})} = 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}, r_{d(a)}, x, S = 100 \left(\frac{\text{cm}}{S} \right); \\ N_{a \equiv \text{Cd}(d \equiv S)} = 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}, r_{a(d)}, x, \quad (42)$$

we propose, at given open circuit voltages: $V_{ocI1(ocI2)}$ and $V_{ocII1(ocII2)}$, the corresponding data of the short circuit current density $J_{scI(II)}$, in order to formulate our following treatment method of two fix points, as:

at $V_{ocI1(ocI2)} = V_{ocII1(ocII2)} = 0.73 \text{ V (0.8759 V)}$, at which

$$J_{scI1(scI2)} = J_{scII1(scII2)} = 21.16 \text{ mA/cm}^2 \text{ (30.25 mA/cm}^2\text{)}, \quad (43)$$

noting that these numerical results are given in Ref. [11], in which the authors assumed that the "quality factor n " is equal to 1.

Now, we define the net current density J at $T=300 \text{ K}$, obtained for the infinite shunt resistance, and expressed as a function of the applied voltage V , flowing through the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $X(x)$ -alloy junction of solar cells, as:

$$J(V) \equiv J_{ph.}(V) - J_{ol(oII)} \times (e^{X_{I(II)}(V)} - 1), \quad X_{I(II)}(V) \equiv \frac{V}{n_{I(II)}(V) \times V_T},$$

$$V_T \equiv \frac{k_B T}{e} = 0.02585 \text{ V}, \quad (44)$$

where the function $n_{I(II)}(V)$ is the photovoltaic conversion factor (PVCF), noting that as $V = V_{oc}$, being the open circuit voltage, $J(V = V_{oc}) = 0$, the photocurrent density is defined by: $J_{ph.}(V = V_{oc}) \equiv J_{scI(scII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc})$, for $V_{oc} \geq V_{ocI1(ocII1)}$.

Therefore, the photovoltaic conversion effect occurs, according to:

$$J_{scI(scII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) \equiv$$

$$\equiv J_{ol(oII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x) \times (e^{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc})} - 1), \quad (45)$$

where $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \equiv n_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc})$, and $X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \equiv \frac{V_{oc}}{n_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \times V_T}$.

Here, one remarks that (i) for a given V_{oc} , both $n_{I(II)}$ and $J_{ol(oII)}$ have the same variations, obtained in the same physical conditions, as observed in the following calculation, (ii) the function $(e^{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc})} - 1)$ or the PVCF, $n_{I(II)}$, representing the photovoltaic conversion effect, converts the light, represented by $J_{scI(scII)}$, into the electricity, by $J_{ol(oII)}$, and finally, for given $(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc})$ -values, $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$ is determined.

Now, for $V_{oc} \geq V_{ocI1(ocII1)}$, one can propose the general expressions for the PVCF, in order to get exactly the values of $n_{I1(II1)}(V_{ocI1(ocII1)})$ and $n_{I2(II2)}(V_{ocI2(ocII2)})$, as functions of V_{oc} , by:

$$n_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) =$$

$$= n_{I1(II1)}(V_{ocI1(ocII1)}) + n_{I2(II2)}(V_{ocI2(ocII2)}) \times \left(\frac{V_{oc}}{V_{ocI1(ocII1)}} - 1 \right)^{\alpha(\beta)}, \quad (46)$$

where, for example, the values of $\alpha(\beta)$, obtained for $x = (0, 0.5 \text{ and } 1)$, will be reported in Tables 2.2 and 3.2 in Appendix 1, for $\text{CdTe}_{1-x}\text{S}_x$ alloy junctions, and in Tables 4.2 and 5.2 in Appendix 1, for

CdTe_{1-x}Se_x, alloy junctions, respectively. One also notes that those $\alpha(\beta)$ -values depend on $(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x)$ -ones.

Tables 2.2 and 3.2, and Tables 4.2 and 5.2, in Appendix 1

So, one can determine the general expressions for the fill factors, as:

$$F_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) = \frac{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) - \ln[X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) + b = 0.72]}{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) + a = 1}, \quad (47)$$

Finally, the efficiency $\eta_{I(II)}$ can be defined in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x) alloy-junction solar cells, by:

$$\eta_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) \equiv \frac{J_{scI(scII)} \times V_{oc} \times F_{I(II)}}{P_{in}}, \quad (48)$$

being assumed to be obtained at 1 sun illumination or at AM1.5G spectrum ($P_{in} = 0.100 \frac{W}{cm^2}$).

It should be noted that the maximal values of $\eta_{I(II)}$, $\eta_{I(II)max}$, are obtained at the corresponding ones of $V_{oc} = V_{ocI(ocII)}$, at which, $\left(\frac{\partial \eta_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, V_{oc})}{\partial V_{oc}} \right)_{V_{oc}=V_{ocI(ocII)}} = 0$, as those given in next

Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2 in Appendix 1, being marked in bold. Further, from the well-known Carnot's theorem, being obtained by the second principle in thermodynamics, or by the entropy law, the maximum efficiency of a heat engine operating between hot (**H**) and cold (**C**) reservoirs is the ratio of the temperature difference between the reservoirs, $T_H - T_C$, to the H-reservoir temperature, T_H , expressed as:

$$\eta_{I(II)max}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, V_{ocI(ocII)}) = 1 - \frac{T_C = 300 \text{ K}}{T_H(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, V_{ocI(ocII)})}. \quad (49)$$

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

We will respectively consider the two following cases of $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ -junctions such as:

HD (Te; Sn) X(x) alloy ER – LD (In; Cd) X(x) – alloy BR –case, according to: 2 (n^+p) – junctions denoted by: (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) , and

HD (In; Cd) X(x) alloy ER – LD (Te; Sn) X(x) – alloy BR –case, according to: 2 (p^+n) – junctions denoted by: (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) .

Now, by using the physical conditions, given in Eq. (42), we can determine various following photovoltaic conversion coefficients.

(I)-X(x) \equiv CdTe_{1-x}S_x – Alloy

Firs case: HD [Te; Sn] X(x) – Alloy ER – LD [In; Cd] X(x) – Alloy BR

Here, there are the 2 (n^+p) – X(x) junctions, being denoted by: (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) .

Then, the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}}$, J_{Bpo} , J_{Eno} and J_{ol} , are calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, and obtained, as those given in Table 2.1 in Appendix 1. Further, those of n_I , J_{scI} , F_I , η_I , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, and reported in the following Table 2.2 in Appendix 1.

Tables 2.1 and 2.2 in Appendix 1

Second case: HD [In ; Cd] X(x) Alloy ER – LD [Te ; Sn] X(x) Alloy BR

Here, there are 2 (p^+n) – X(x) junctions, being denoted by: (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn).

Then, the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}}, J_{Bno}, J_{Epo}$ and J_{oII} , are calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, and obtained, as those given in Table 3.1 in Appendix 1. Further, those of $n_{II}, J_{scII}, F_{II}, \eta_{II}$, and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, and reported in the following Table 3.2 in Appendix 1.

Tables 3.1 and 3.2 in Appendix 1

(2) –X(x)≡ CdTe_{1-x}Se_x – Alloy

Firs case: HD [Te ; Sn] X(x) Alloy ER – LD [In ; Cd] X(x) Alloy BR

Here, there are the 2 (n^+p) – X(x) junctions, being denoted by: (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd).

Then, from above physical conditions, given in Eq. (42), the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}}, J_{Bpo}, J_{Eno}$ and J_{oI} , are calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, and obtained, as those given in Table 4.1 in Appendix 1. Further, those of $n_I, J_{scI}, F_I, \eta_I$ and T_H are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, and reported in the following Table 4.2 in Appendix 1.

Tables 4.1 and 4.2 in Appendix 1

Second case: HD [In ; Cd] X(x) Alloy ER – LD [Te ; Sn] X(x) Alloy BR

Here, there are 2 (p^+n) – X(x) junctions, being denoted by: (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn).

Then, from above physical conditions, the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}}, J_{Bno}, J_{Epo}$ and J_{oII} , are calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, and obtained, as those given in Table 5.1 in Appendix 1. Further, those of $n_{II}, J_{scII}, F_{II}, \eta_I$ and T_H are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, and reported in the following Table 5.2 in Appendix 1.

Tables 5.1 and 5.2 in Appendix 1

Finally, some concluding remarks, obtained from those numerical results reported in above Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2, are discussed as follows.

(i)-As noted in Tables 2.1, 3.1, 4.1 and 5.1, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density $J_{ol(oII)}$ decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x, and decreases strongly with increasing x, for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. Then, as remarked in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2, at a same V_{oc} , the photovoltaic conversion factor, $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$, decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x, but it decreases strongly with increasing x, for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. In other words, as discussed in Eq. (45), at a same V_{oc} , both $J_{ol(oII)}$ and $n_{I(II)}$ have the same variations for same physical conditions.

(ii)-With such variations of $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$, as observed in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2, the maximal values of $\eta_{I(II)}, \eta_{I(II)max.}$, and the corresponding ones of the H-reservoir temperature, T_H , are obtained at $V_{oc} = V_{ocI(ocII)}$, being marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius.

(iii)-In particular, at x=0, both $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdTe_{1-x}S_x(Se_x) alloys become the CdTe-crystal, as observed in Tables 1.1 and 1.2, and therefore, as given in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2, and 5.2, we get the same numerical results of $\eta_{I(max.)(II(max.))}$ [=26.182 % (25.92 %)], which can also be compared with the corresponding ones given in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ crystalline CdTe-junction solar cells [1, 2], as: $\eta_{I(max.)(II(max.))} = 23.14 \% (25.90 \%)$.

(iv)-Further, at x=1 and for Sn⁺Cd (Cd⁺Sn), we obtain: (a) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdTe_{1-x}S_x alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I(max.)(II(max.))}$ =34.151 % (33.93 %) and T_H =455.6 K (454.1 K), as those given in Tables 2.2 (3.2), and (b) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdTe_{1-x}Se_x alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I(max.)(II(max.))}$ =28.23 % (28.22 %) and T_H =418.0 K (417.9 K), as those given in Tables 4.2 (5.2).

(v)- Finally, from above remarks (iii) and (iv), we can conclude that in order to obtain the highest efficiencies, the present ($CdTe_{1-x}S_x$, $CdTe_{1-x}Se_x$)- crystalline alloy junction solar cells could be chosen rather than the crystalline CdTe-junction solar cell [1, 2].

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APPENDIX 1

Table 1.1 From Equations (5, 8a, 8b, 9) and in the n(p)-type $CdTe_{1-x}S_x$ -alloy, the numerical results of the energy-band-structure parameters, reported below, suggest that, with increasing x and $r_{d(a)}$, both $B_{do(ao)}(x)$ and $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ decrease, while the other ones increase

Donor		S	Se	Te	Sn
r_d (nm)	\nearrow	0.104	0.114	$r_{do}=0.132$	0.140
x	\nearrow	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1
$B_{do}(x)$ in 10^8 (N/m ²)	\nearrow			2.02, 3.54, 5.50	
$\varepsilon(r_d, x)$	\searrow	12.9, 12.12, 11.30	11.22, 10.5, 9.78	10.31, 9.655, 9	10.14, 9.495, 8.85
$E_d(r_d, x)$ meV	\nearrow	7.71, 13.5, 21.0	10.3, 18.0, 27.9	12.2, 21.3, 33.1	12.6, 22, 34.2
$E_{gn}(r_d, x)$ eV	\nearrow	1.62, 2.09, 2.568	1.62, 2.098, 2.575	1.622, 2.101, 2.58	1.6224, 2.102, 2.581
$E_{gin}(T = 300K, r_d, x)$ eV	\nearrow	1.52, 1.96, 2.41	1.52, 1.968, 2.415	1.522, 1.971, 2.42	1.5224, 1.972, 2.421
Acceptor		Ga	Mg	In	Cd
r_d (nm)	\nearrow	0.126	0.140	0.144	$r_{ao}=0.148$
x	\nearrow	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1
$B_{do}(x)$ in 10^8 (N/m ²)	\nearrow				12.4, 13.95, 15.87
$\varepsilon(r_d, x)$	\searrow	11.4, 10.7, 9.97	10.44, 9.78, 9.12	10.34, 9.69, 9.03	10.31, 9.655, 9
$E_d(r_d, x)$ meV	\nearrow	85.5, 96.4, 109.6	102.2, 115, 131	104.2, 117, 133.6	104.9, 118.2, 134.5
$E_{gn}(r_d, x)$ eV	\nearrow	1.60, 2.08, 2.55	1.62, 2.098, 2.577	1.621, 2.100, 2.579	1.622, 2.101, 2.58
$E_{gin}(T = 300K, r_d, x)$ eV	\nearrow	1.50, 1.95, 2.39	1.52, 1.968, 2.417	1.521, 1.970, 2.419	1.522, 1.971, 2.42

Table 1.2 From Equations (5, 8a, 8b, 9) and in the n(p)-type $CdTe_{1-x}Se_x$ -alloy, the numerical results of the energy-band-structure parameters, reported below, suggest that, with increasing x and $r_{d(a)}$, both $B_{do(ao)}(x)$ and $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ decrease, while the other ones increase

Donor		S	Se	Te	Sn
r_d (nm)	↗	0.104	0.114	$r_{do}=0.132$	0.140
x	↗	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1
$B_{do}(x)$ in 10^8 (N/m ²)	↗			2.02, 2.20, 2.39	
$\varepsilon(r_d, x)$	↘	12.94, 12.87, 12.80	11.22, 11.16, 11.11	10.31, 10.255, 10.2	10.14, 10.08, 10.03
$E_d(r_d, x)$ meV	↗	7.713, 8.41, 9.12	10.3, 11.2, 12.1	12.2, 13.3, 14.4	12.6, 13.7, 14.9
$E_{gn}(r_d, x)$ eV	↗	1.618, 1.726, 1.835	1.620, 1.729, 1.838	1.622, 1.731, 1.84	1.6224, 1.7315, 1.8405
$E_{gin}(T = 300K, r_d, x)$ eV	↗	1.518, 1.626, 1.735	1.520, 1.629, 1.738	1.522, 1.631, 1.74	1.6314, 1.6314, 1.7405
Acceptor		Ga	Mg	In	Cd
r_a (nm)	↗	0.126	0.140	0.144	$r_{ao}=0.148$
x	↗	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1	0,0.5,1
$B_{do}(x)$ in 10^8 (N/m ²)	↗				12.4, 9.69, 6.94
$\varepsilon(r_d, x)$	↘	11.4, 10.36, 11.30	10.44, 10.39, 10.33	10.34, 10.29, 10.23	10.31, 10.255, 10.2
$E_d(r_d, x)$ meV	↗	85.5, 66.9, 47.9	102.2, 80, 57.3	104.2, 81.6, 58.4	104.9, 82.1, 58.8
$E_{gn}(r_d, x)$ eV	↗	1.60, 1.716, 1.829	1.619, 1.729, 1.838	1.621, 1.730, 1.839	1.622, 1.731, 1.84
$E_{gin}(T = 300K, r_d, x)$ eV	↗	1.50, 1.616, 1.729	1.519, 1.629, 1.738	1.521, 1.630, 1.739	1.522, 1.631, 1.74

Table 2.1 In the HD [(Te; Sn)- CdTe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] ER-LD[(In; Cd)-CdTe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{hEt}^*}{\tau_{hE}}$, J_{Bpo} , J_{Eno} and J_{ol} , are computed, using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, noting that J_{ol} decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x, but it increases strongly with increasing x for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius, being new results

n^+p		Te^+In	Sn^+Cd
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{hEt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition.			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-20} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.4113	2.4035
J_{Eno} in 10^{-30} (A/cm ²)	↗	2.3329	2.3820
J_{ol} in 10^{-20} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.4113	2.4035
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{hEt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition.			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-27} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.2797	1.2755
J_{Eno} in 10^{-33} (A/cm ²)	↗	2.8961	2.9079
J_{ol} in 10^{-27} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.2797	1.2755
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{hEt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition.			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-35} (A/cm ²)	↘	5.5667	5.5486
J_{Eno} in 10^{-38} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.0295	1.0107
J_{ol} in 10^{-35} (A/cm ²)	↘	5.5667	5.5486

Table 2.2 In the HD [(Te; Sn)- CdTe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] ER-LD[(In; Cd)-CdTeS_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of n_I , J_{scI} , F_I , η_I , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, noting that both $\eta_{I_{max}}$ and T_H , marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{d(\alpha)}$, being new results

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_I	$J_{scI}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	$F_I(\%)$	$\eta_I(\%)$
Here, $x=0$. For the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.1392$.				
n^+p	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$
0.73	0.6831; 0.6830	21.6; 21.6	88.81; 88.81	14.00; 14.00
0.818	0.7561; 0.7560	35.99; 35.998	88.91; 88.91	26.18; 26.181
0.819	0.7570; 0.7569	36.95; 35.955	88.91; 88.91	26.181; 26.182
$V_{ocI} = 0.819 V$				$T_H(K) = 406.4; 406.4$
0.820	0.7579; 0.7579	35.91; 35.909	88.91; 88.91	26.18; 26.181
0.8759	0.8129; 0.8128	30.31; 30.311	88.88; 88.88	23.59; 23.596
2	2.2107; 2.2105	0.038; 0.038	87.29; 87.29	0.066; 0.0662
Here, $x=0.5$. For the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.131$.				
n^+p	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$
0.73	0.4861; 0.486	21.6; 21.6	91.41; 91.41	14.41; 14.414
0.807	0.5316; 0.5316	40.34; 40.34	91.48; 91.48	29.782; 29.783
0.808	0.5323; 0.5323	40.29; 40.29	91.48; 91.48	29.783; 29.784
$V_{ocI} = 0.808 V$				$T_H(K) = 427.2; 427.2$
0.809	0.5330; 0.5329	40.24; 40.24	91.48; 91.48	29.781; 29.782
0.8759	0.5799; 0.5799	30.04; 30.045	91.45; 91.45	24.066; 24.0666
1	0.6743; 0.6743	10.40; 10.397	91.33; 91.33	9.4956; 9.4952
Here, $x=1$. For the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.1272$.				
n^+p	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+In; Sn^+Cd$
0.73	0.3763; 0.3763	21.6; 21.6	92.99; 92.99	14.66; 14.66
0.801	0.4088; 0.4088	45.81; 45.81	93.05; 93.05	34.146; 34.147
0.802	0.4093; 0.4093	45.76; 45.76	93.05; 93.05	34.150; 34.151
$V_{ocI} = 0.802 V$				$T_H(K) = 455.6; 455.6$
0.803	0.4098; 0.4098	45.70; 45.70	93.05; 93.05	34.148; 34.149
0.8759	0.4495; 0.4495	30.21; 30.208	93.02; 93.02	24.612; 24.6123
1	0.5228; 0.5227	7.561; 7.560	92.91; 92.91	7.025; 7.0246

Table 3.1 In the HD [(In; Cd)- CdTe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Te; Sn)-CdTe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}}$, J_{Bno} , J_{Epo} , and J_{oII} are computed, using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, noting that J_{oII} decreases slightly with increasing $r_{a(d)}$ -radius for given x, but it increases strongly with increasing x for given $r_{a(d)}$ -radius, being new results

p^n		In^+Te	Cd^+Sn
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-21} (A/cm ²)	↘	8.8400	8.5549
J_{Epo} in 10^{-20} (A/cm ²)	↘	5.9078	5.7533
J_{oII} in 10^{-20} (A/cm ²)	↘	6.7919	6.6088
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (34), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-28} (A/cm ²)	↘	4.7484	4.5402
J_{Epo} in 10^{-27} (A/cm ²)	↘	3.1691	3.0762
J_{oII} in 10^{-27} (A/cm ²)	↘	3.6439	3.5302
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (34), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-35} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.0979	1.9750
J_{Epo} in 10^{-34} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.3943	1.3480
J_{oII} in 10^{-34} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.6041	1.5455

Table 3.2 In the HD [(In; Cd)-CdTe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Te; Sn)-CdTeS_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of n_{II} , J_{scII} , F_{II} , η_{II} , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, noting that both η_{IImax} and T_H , marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{a(d)}$, being new results

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_{II}	$J_{scII}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	$F_{II}(\%)$	$\eta_{II}(\%)$
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.13965$.				
p^+n	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.7006; 0.7001	21.6; 21.6	88.59; 88.59	13.97; 13.97
0.81	0.7677; 0.7672	35.93; 35.94	88.69; 88.70	25.81; 25.83
0.82	0.7773; 0.7768	35.63; 35.64	88.69; 88.70	25.91; 25.92
$V_{ocII} = 0.82 V$				$T_H(K) = 404.9; 405.0$
0.83	0.7871; 0.7866	35.07; 35.08	88.66; 88.70	25.81; 25.82
0.8759	0.8337; 0.8331	30.25; 30.26	88.88; 88.66	23.49; 23.50
2	2.2676; 2.2661	0.044; 0.0442	87.04; 87.05	0.077; 0.077
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.132$				
p^+n	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.4950; 0.4947	21.6; 21.6	91.29; 91.29	14.39; 14.39
0.80	0.5365; 0.5362	40.52; 40.53	91.36; 91.37	29.62; 29.63
0.81	0.5433; 0.5430	40.21; 40.22	91.36; 91.37	29.76; 29.77
$V_{ocII} = 0.81 V$				$T_H(K) = 427.1; 427.2$
0.82	0.5502; 0.5499	39.44; 39.45	91.36; 91.36	29.54; 29.55
0.8759	0.5904; 0.5901	30.34; 30.35	91.33; 91.33	24.27; 24.28
2	1.6001; 1.5992	0.004; 0.004	90.08; 90.09	0.006; 0.006
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.1275$.				
p^+n	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.3817; 0.3815	21.6; 21.6	92.91; 92.92	14.65; 14.65
0.802	0.4151; 0.4149	45.49; 45.50	92.97; 92.97	33.91; 33.92
0.803	0.4156; 0.4154	45.43; 45.45	92.97; 92.97	33.92; 33.93
$V_{ocII} = 0.803 V$				$T_H(K) = 454.0; 454.1$
0.804	0.4162; 0.4160	45.37; 45.38	92.97; 92.97	33.91; 33.92
0.8759	0.4559; 0.4556	30.26; 30.27	92.94; 92.94	24.64; 24.64
0.90	0.4698; 0.4696	24.19; 24.19	92.92; 92.92	20.23; 20.23

Table 4.1. In the HD [(Te; Sn)-CdTe_{1-x}Se_x-alloy] ER-LD[(In; Cd)-CdTe_{1-x}Se_x-alloy] BR and for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{hlt}^*}{\tau_{hE}}$, J_{Bpo} , J_{Eno} , and J_{ol} are computed, using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, noting that J_{ol} decreases slightly for given x with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x, but it increases strongly with increasing x for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius

n^+p		Te^+In	Sn^+Cd
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{hlt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-20} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.4113	2.4035
J_{Eno} in 10^{-30} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.3329	2.3820
J_{ol} in 10^{-20} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.4113	2.4035
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{hlt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-22} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.7139	2.7050
J_{Eno} in 10^{-31} (A/cm ²)	↗	1.9947	2.0271
J_{ol} in 10^{-22} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.7139	2.7050
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{hlt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.6523	2.6437
J_{Eno} in 10^{-32} (A/cm ²)	↗	1.0818	1.0940
J_{ol} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.6523	2.6437

Table 4.2. In the HD [(Te; Sn)-CdTe_{1-x}Se_x-alloy] ER-LD[(In; Cd)-CdTe_{1-x}Se_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of n_I , J_{scl} , F_I , η_I , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, noting that both $\eta_{I_{max}}$ and T_H , marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{d(\alpha)}$, being new results

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_I	$J_{scl}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	$F_I(\%)$	$\eta_I(\%)$
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$. For the (Te ⁺ In, Sn ⁺ Cd)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.1392$.				
n^+p	Te ⁺ In; Sn ⁺ Cd			
0.73	0.6831; 0.6830	21.6; 21.6	88.81; 88.81	14.00; 14.00
0.818	0.7561; 0.7560	35.99; 35.998	88.91; 88.91	26.18; 26.181
0.819	0.7570; 0.7569	35.95; 35.955	88.91; 88.91	26.181; 26.182
$V_{ocI} = 0.819 V$				$T_H(K) = 406.4; 406.4$
0.820	0.7579; 0.7579	35.91; 35.909	88.91; 88.91	26.18; 26.181
0.8759	0.8129; 0.8128	30.31; 30.311	88.88; 88.88	23.59; 23.596
1	0.9449; 0.9448	14.46; 14.46	88.72; 88.72	12.83; 12.83
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$. For the (Te ⁺ In, Sn ⁺ Cd)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.1365$.				
n^+p	Te ⁺ In; Sn ⁺ Cd			
0.73	0.6162; 0.6161	21.6; 21.6	89.66; 89.66	14.14; 14.14
0.814	0.6790; 0.6790	37.14; 37.14	89.76; 89.76	27.14; 27.14
0.815	0.6799; 0.6798	37.10; 37.10	89.76; 89.76	27.141; 27.142
$V_{ocI} = 0.815 V$				$T_H(K) = 411.7; 411.7$
0.816	0.6807; 0.6807	37.05; 37.06	89.75; 89.76	27.14; 27.14
0.8759	0.7339; 0.7339	30.27; 30.27	89.72; 89.72	23.79; 23.79
1	0.8532; 0.8531	13.25; 13.25	89.58; 89.58	11.87; 11.87
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$. For the (Te ⁺ In, Sn ⁺ Cd)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.1345$.				
n^+p	Te ⁺ In; Sn ⁺ Cd			
0.73	0.5596; 0.5596	21.6; 21.6	90.41; 90.41	14.25; 14.25
0.811	0.6147; 0.6147	38.46; 38.46	90.49; 90.49	28.22; 28.22
0.812	0.6155; 0.6154	38.42; 38.42	90.49; 90.49	28.23; 28.23
$V_{ocI} = 0.812 V$				$T_H(K) = 418.0; 418.0$
0.813	0.6163; 0.6162	38.37; 38.37	90.49; 90.49	28.22; 28.23
0.8759	0.6670; 0.6670	30.34; 30.34	90.46; 90.46	24.04; 24.04
1	0.7755; 0.7754	12.16; 12.16	90.32; 90.32	10.98; 10.98

Table 5.1 In the HD [(In; Cd)-CdTe_{1-x}Se_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Te; Sn)-CdTe_{1-x}Se_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}}$, J_{Bno} , J_{Epo} , and J_{oII} are computed, using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, noting that J_{oII} decreases slightly with increasing $r_{a(d)}$ -radius for given x, but it increases strongly with increasing x for given $r_{a(d)}$ -radius, being new results

p^n		In^+Te	Cd^+Sn
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-21} (A/cm ²)	↘	8.8400	8.5549
J_{Epo} in 10^{-20} (A/cm ²)	↘	5.9078	5.7533
J_{oII} in 10^{-20} (A/cm ²)	↘	6.7918	6.6088
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (34), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-23} (A/cm ²)	↘	9.9636	9.6284
J_{Epo} in 10^{-22} (A/cm ²)	↘	3.5000	3.4292
J_{oII} in 10^{-22} (A/cm ²)	↘	4.4963	4.3921
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (34), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-25} (A/cm ²)	↘	9.7523	9.4102
J_{Epo} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.0790	1.0638
J_{oII} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.0542	2.0048

Table 5.2 In the HD [(In; Cd)-CdTe_{1-x}Se_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Te; Sn)-CdTeSe_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of n_{II} , J_{scII} , F_{II} , η_{II} , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, noting that both η_{IImax} and T_H , marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{a(d)}$, being new results

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_{II}	$J_{scII}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	$F_{II}(\%)$	$\eta_{II}(\%)$
Here, $x=0$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.13965$				
p^+n	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.7006; 0.7001	21.6; 21.6	88.59; 88.59	13.97; 13.97
0.81	0.7677; 0.7672	35.93; 35.94	88.69; 88.70	25.81; 25.83
0.82	0.7773; 0.7768	35.63; 35.64	88.69; 88.70	25.91; 25.92
$V_{ocII} = 0.82 V$				$T_H(K) = 404.9; 405.0$
0.83	0.7871; 0.7866	35.07; 35.08	88.66; 88.70	25.81; 25.82
0.8759	0.8337; 0.8331	30.25; 30.26	88.88; 88.66	23.49; 23.50
2	2.2676; 2.2661	0.044; 0.0442	87.04; 87.05	0.077; 0.077
Here, $x=0.5$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.1367$				
p^+n	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.6230; 0.6227	21.6; 21.6	89.57; 89.58	14.12; 14.12
0.81	0.6831; 0.6828	37.14; 37.15	89.67; 89.67	26.97; 26.98
0.82	0.6918; 0.6914	36.70; 36.71	89.67; 89.67	26.99; 27.00
$V_{ocII} = 0.81 V$				$T_H(K) = 410.9; 410.9$
0.83	0.7005; 0.7001	35.97; 35.98	89.66; 89.66	26.77; 26.78
0.8759	0.7420; 0.7417	30.25; 30.25	89.63; 89.64	23.75; 23.75
1	0.8626; 0.8622	13.37; 13.37	89.49; 89.49	11.97; 11.96
Here, $x=1$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.13415$				
p^+n	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.5568; 0.5566	21.6; 21.6	90.44; 90.45	14.26; 14.26
0.80	0.6033; 0.6030	38.66; 38.67	90.53; 90.53	28.00; 28.01
0.81	0.6109; 0.6106	38.48; 38.49	90.53; 90.53	28.21; 28.22
$V_{ocII} = 0.81 V$				$T_H(K) = 417.9; 417.9$
0.82	0.6186; 0.6183	37.89; 37.90	90.53; 90.53	28.13; 28.13
0.8759	0.6637; 0.6634	30.25; 30.25	90.49; 90.50	23.98; 23.98
1	0.7716; 0.7713	12.06; 12.06	90.34; 90.36	10.90; 10.90

